

Assessing Farmers' Livelihood Vulnerability to Climate Change: A Case Study of Lower Niumi and Sabach Sanjal, The Gambia

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Abstract

In The Gambia, farmers primarily depend on rainfed agriculture and encounter significant climate vulnerabilities, including flooding and extended dry periods, which jeopardize food security and threaten their livelihoods. This study aims to evaluate the livelihood vulnerability of smallholder farmers in The Gambia by applying the Livelihood Vulnerability Index (LVI) to compare two districts: Lower Niumi and Sabach Sanjal. These two districts represent a significant portion of the region characterized by a high percentage of households involved in agricultural activities. While Lower Niumi is classified as a coastal region, Sabach Sanjal is situated inland; both districts are adversely affected by the impacts of climate change. The LVI is divided into the three main components of vulnerability identified by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC): exposure, sensitivity, and adaptive capacity. Data was gathered through household surveys involving 239 smallholder farmers, alongside key informant interviews with community leaders and Ministry of Agriculture (MOA) officials. The results indicate that Lower Niumi exhibits greater vulnerability than Sabach Sanjal, particularly regarding food security, water, and knowledge and skills. Meanwhile, Sabach Sanjal faces significant challenges in health, social networks, and housing stability. The LVI-IPCC scores show that Lower Niumi has a higher exposure score (0.374) than Sabach Sanjal (0.289), indicating its increased susceptibility to climate-related hazards. Both districts have similar adaptive capacity scores (0.406 and 0.403), reflecting comparable resilience to climate impacts. However, sensitivity analysis suggests that Lower Niumi (0.338) is more vulnerable to climate change than Sabach Sanjal (0.295). Importantly, all farmers in Lower Niumi (100%) and 98% in Sabach Sanjal depend on their family farms for food. Yet, only 2% and 18% of farmers in these districts, respectively, cultivate rice, the staple food of The Gambia.

Keywords: *Climate change, Resilience, Risk, Livelihood vulnerability, Smallholder farmers, The Gambia.*

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Introduction

The rapid advancement of climate change poses significant threats to agricultural productivity and food security worldwide (Bekuma et al., 2023). These vulnerabilities have manifested in the form of elevated temperatures, erratic precipitation patterns, and an increased frequency of severe drought events. Such

climatic changes have an adverse impact on agricultural productivity, with temperature fluctuations contributing to an increase in the prevalence of crop pests (Dore, 2005; Kalele et al., 2021).

Climate change has emerged as a significant developmental challenge, particularly for developing economies in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), which rely predominantly on rain-fed agriculture for their socioeconomic advancement (Adzawla et al., 2020). Studies have demonstrated the severe impacts of climate change in SSA, including prolonged dry spells, erratic rainfall patterns, and heat stress, which contribute to diminished crop yields in both quality and quantity (Ayanlade et al., 2022; Cuthbert et al., 2019). SSA is one of the smallest contributors to global warming; however, the region remains highly vulnerable to climate change due to low economic development, high dependence on natural resources for agricultural production, and limited technological advancements (Adzawla et al., 2019).

Climate change in SSA is also linked to an increase in vector-borne illnesses, such as malaria, Rift Valley fever, schistosomiasis, lymphatic filariasis, and African trypanosomiasis (Muia et al., 2025).

These climatic impacts have disrupted the availability of food commodities in the market, leading to price fluctuations that disproportionately affect smallholder farmers across the region (Easterling et al., 2007). Smallholder farmers in SSA are particularly affected due to their limited access to weather and market information, insufficient resources, and strong reliance on climate-sensitive activities (Oyarzo et al., 2024). In contrast to their counterparts, smallholder farmers often exhibit inadequate land tenure practices, limited access to financial resources, and a lower rate of households achieving formal education. This lack of formal education significantly hinders their ability to access reliable information about climate variations and change (Awazi et al., 2020).

The impact of climate change negatively affects the livelihoods of smallholder farmers by causing a noticeable decline in wages, labor supply, and overall market income, which in turn reduces their ability to support their families and invest in their farms (Belford et al., 2023). These adverse consequences impact society both directly and indirectly, leading to job and income losses and increasing the risk of food insecurity, which leaves small-scale farmers vulnerable.

Figure 1. Monthly Climatology of Average Minimum Surface Air Temperature, Average Mean Surface Air Temperature, Average Maximum Surface Air Temperature and Precipitation 1991-2020

The agricultural sector in The Gambia contributes 28 percent to the GDP and employs approximately 70 percent of the labor force (Sanyang and Saine, 2022). The Gambia stands among the most vulnerable nations in sub-Saharan Africa to the effects of climate change, due to the frequent occurrence of natural disasters and the country's heavy dependence on rainfall and natural resources for agricultural production (MECCNAR, 2024).

The country faces significant challenges to climate variation and changes due to its growing population, struggling economy, and deteriorating environmental conditions (UNDP, 2015). The impacts of climate change have a significant effect on the well-being of the Gambian population and the nation's economy. Increased flooding leads to infrastructure degradation and road damage, while declines in agricultural productivity exacerbate concerns about food security. Rising temperatures and increased aridity pose substantial risks to public health. These multifaceted impacts serve to exacerbate the existing stresses associated with high poverty levels and economic volatility in the country (Urquhart, 2016).

Declining rainfall levels and mid-season dry spells, primarily attributed to the effects of climate change, have heightened The Gambia's susceptibility to drought hazards. Although drought occurrences in The Gambia exist at moderate levels of the Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI) values (-1.00 to -1.49) and the Vegetation Condition Index (VCI) readings of less than 35%, the North Bank, the region under study, stands out as the most susceptible territory (Bayo and Mahmood, 2023).

The study area is characterized as the most agriculturally reliant region, while simultaneously being one of the most vulnerable areas to climate change and its variabilities within the country. This vulnerability is primarily attributed to its significant dependence on rain-fed agriculture, coupled with unpredictable weather patterns, extended dry spells, recurrent droughts, elevated temperatures, and the encroachment of saltwater (Ceesay et al., 2024; GBoS, 2024; Kutir et al., 2015; Yaffa, 2013). The essential relationship between climate change and agricultural practices in the North Bank Region necessitates a thorough investigation to identify adaptive measures that can safeguard the farmers in this area. It is in this vein that this study aims to assess the livelihood vulnerability of smallholder farmers in Lower Nuimi and Sabach, two distinct districts within the North Bank Region. Lower Nuimi is located in the coastal zone of The Gambia, while Sabach Sanjal is situated inland, bordered by the River Gambia to the south and Senegal to the north. Recently, many climate-related studies have been conducted in the North Bank Region of The Gambia, driven by the region's vulnerability to climate change. However, most of these studies do not focus on the vulnerability of farmers' livelihoods, particularly smallholder farmers, to climate change. To some extent, livelihood vulnerabilities have been researched in The Gambia; however, the emphasis of most of these studies remains on the coastal zones.

Literature Review

The concept of vulnerability has been explored across various research traditions; however, a consensus regarding its precise definition remains elusive (Gallopín, 2006). Adger (2006), conceptualized it as the condition of being susceptible to harm due to exposure to environmental and social changes, compounded by a lack of adaptive capacity (Adger, 2006). It is also defined as the extent to which a system is prone to adverse effects of climate change, including climate variability and extremes (Füssel and Klein, 2006). It depends on the characteristics, magnitude, and rate of climate change and variation to which a system is exposed, its sensitivity, and its ability to adapt to these changes (Smit et al., 2000).

A system's vulnerability arises from its likelihood of being affected by external threats based on its exposure, sensitivity, and adaptive abilities. Systems experience negative impacts when they come into contact with threats such as droughts, conflicts, socio-economic conditions, and environmental factors. The severity of the impact on the system depends on its exposure and its coping mechanisms and adaptation capabilities (Bizikova, 2009).

The degree to which communities are vulnerable to climate change impacts determines the extent to which they are affected during extreme weather events. Various levels of vulnerability emerge between communities due to differences in natural resource availability and geographical position. Several factors, including floods and riverbank erosion, food insecurity, livelihood diversification, deficiencies in communication networks, market access, and essential services, affect the population (Al Mamun et al., 2023).

Vulnerability evaluation has evolved from an initial top-down, biophysical approach focused on climate hazard exposure to a more comprehensive bottom-up framework that incorporates the social and contextual factors influencing vulnerability across different communities. This dynamic understanding of vulnerability is shaped by various influences, including socioeconomic conditions, governance, and environmental changes (IPCC, 2022). As a result, vulnerability and adaptation (V&A) assessments have become increasingly intricate, supported by numerous frameworks, approaches, and tools. There is no perfect method for conducting these assessments; deciding which approach to use depends on the specific circumstances (UNFCCC, 2021). Many studies rely heavily on the IPCC's working definition of vulnerability, which is a function of exposure, sensitivity, and adaptive capacity (Hahn et al., 2009).

According to the IPCC 2022 report on vulnerability, the term "adaptation" is defined as the adjustments deployed in response to observed or anticipated impacts of climate change. "Exposure" denotes the extent to which a system—be it a community, ecosystem, or economic structure—is susceptible to climate-related hazards. "Sensitivity" refers to the degree to which a system is influenced by climate change. The probability of experiencing negative climate impacts increases with greater exposure levels, and so does the magnitude of adverse effects due to sensitivity risk factors. Together, exposure and sensitivity define the complete risks that affect a system. "Risk" is conceptualized as the potential for loss or damage arising from the interplay of exposure and sensitivity to climate hazards. Relevant adaptation strategies enhance resilience, thereby strengthening the systems' capabilities to address climate change effectively. As outlined in Figure 2, resilience enables systems to withstand changes without requiring major adaptations, as it reduces the need for extensive adjustments. It is defined as the capacity of a system to absorb disturbances, adjust to evolving conditions, and recuperate from adverse events while maintaining its fundamental functions and structures (IPCC, 2022).

Figure 2. The Interrelationship between Determinants of Vulnerability

Livelihood Vulnerability Index

The LVI framework, developed by Hahn et al. (2009), provides a comprehensive system for measuring livelihood vulnerability to climate change through social, economic, and environmental indicators. It evaluates exposure to natural disasters and climate variability, sensitivity related to food security, water access, and health, as well as adaptive capacity through socio-demographic profiles and livelihood strategies. This framework presents two methods: a composite index of key components and alignment with the IPCC's three vulnerability factors—exposure, sensitivity, and adaptive capacity. The scoring scale ranges from -1 (indicating low vulnerability) to +1 (indicating high vulnerability), providing a consistent evaluation that is beneficial for policymakers, development agencies, and public health experts (Mukherjee and Siddique, 2020).

The LVI serves as a fundamental interdisciplinary assessment tool for livelihood vulnerability because it contains important defining characteristics. Firstly, it works within the framework of the IPCC to provide an efficient approach for analyzing natural disaster exposure alongside climate change exposure, adaptive capabilities, and sensitivity. The framework provides a structured approach to examining the fundamentals of livelihoods, along with their environmental components. It comprises various indicators that are used to measure both environmental exposure and the socioeconomic aspects that influence adaptability levels (Adu et al., 2018; Hahn et al., 2009). Secondly, the LVI enhances its analytical strength by monitoring social, infrastructural, economic, and institutional types of vulnerability. Each category utilizes specific major indicators, such as social networks for social vulnerability and land tenure for infrastructural vulnerability. Institutional and economic vulnerabilities can be assessed using indicators such as natural disaster and climate variability, as well as livelihood strategies (Rana and Routray, 2018).

Thirdly, the LVI is flexible, allowing for the customization of components and sub-indicators to fit specific environmental and situational contexts. Researchers like (Amuzu et al., 2018; Botero and Salinas, 2013; Shah et al., 2013), have expanded the index to address unique regional challenges, such as the economic difficulties faced by Indian farmers, making it applicable to different geographical locations and climatic conditions. Due to its advantages, researchers globally have utilized the LVI and continue to do so. For instance, Hahn et al. (2009) developed and tested the index in Mozambique, examining one coastal district and another inland. Shah et al. (2013) applied the LVI within a Caribbean climate, focusing on two wetland communities in Trinidad and Tobago. More recently, Oyarzo et al. (2024) employed the index to assess the livelihood vulnerability of farmers in the Global South, specifically within the Chilean Winter Rainfall-Valdivian Forest. Similarly, our research focuses on two districts in The Gambia, one characterized by coastal features and the other representing an inland community. Finally, the LVI provides policymakers with an essential tool for decision support through its community-level analysis of vulnerability factors based on demographics and social characteristics (Hahn et al., 2009; Oyarzo et al., 2024).

Methodology

Study Area

Lower Nuimi and Sabach Sanjal, located in the Kerewan Local Government Area of The Gambia's North Bank Region, are the focus of this study. According to the Gambia Bureau of Statistics (GBoS, 2024), 91.6% of the population in this region engages in agriculture for their livelihood. The region, situated between latitudes 13°25' N and 13°40' N and longitudes 16°00' W and 16°35' W, falls within the Sudan-Sahelian climatic zone, with annual rainfall from 600 to 900 mm. The region is known as the most vulnerable in The Gambia to environmental pressures, such as drought and irregular rainfall, threatening farmers' livelihoods more than in other regions (Kutir et al., 2015).

Figure 3. Map of the Two Districts

Agricultural dependence within the region poses significant challenges to the local population, according to Yaffa (2013). Agricultural management in most fields relies on rainwater, making these communities highly vulnerable to unpredictable weather patterns and the effects of climate change. A study by Kutir et al. (2015) indicates that the North Bank Region of The Gambia is the most environmentally vulnerable area, characterized by extreme drought, unpredictable rainfall levels, and higher temperatures, among its five administrative regions. The local climate poses severe agricultural challenges, which now endanger farmers to a higher degree than elsewhere in The Gambia. Rains becoming unpredictable and temperature increases produce extensive impacts that force farmers to modify their established farming practices and crop choices. Soil fertility suffers significant harm due to increased salinity from saltwater intrusion, which exacerbates the decline in agricultural productivity. The combination of these phenomena results in declining crop production yields and endangered livestock health, causing detrimental economic effects and reduced food security among local communities (Ceesay et al., 2024).

Sampling Methods

The study primarily drew on data collected from smallholder farmers through a thoughtfully designed questionnaire that was created, tested, and administered to household heads in the study area. This questionnaire included nine major components and 40 sub-indicators used to calculate the LVI for the analysis. To choose research participants, a multistage cluster sampling approach was utilized. The first phase involved purposive sampling of two districts, Lower Nuimi and Sabach Sanjal, located in the North Bank Region of The Gambia. Subsequently, a simple random sampling method was used to select five villages from each district for data collection. In the last phase, households were identified through simple random sampling by performing a random walk along the primary streets of the communities. The sample size for the research was determined using Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) formula for sample size, as shown in Eq. (1). As indicated in Table 1, a total of 239 heads of households participated in the study. To find the number of respondents required from each community, the total number of households in that community was divided by the overall count of 632 households in the study area and subsequently multiplied by 239.

$$S = \frac{X^2 NP(1-P)}{d^2(N-1)+X^2P(1-P)} \quad (1)$$

Where: S stands for the required sample size, X² indicates the Z value (when using 1.96 in the calculation, we have a 95% confidence level). N represents the total population, whereas P stands for the expected proportion, which is 0.5 or 50%, and d symbolizes the accuracy level, which equals 0.05, corresponding to a 5% accuracy margin.

Table 1. Sample Respondents for the Two Districts

Districts	Village Name	Total Household	Sampled Households	Percentage
Lower Nuimi	Njongon	104	39	16
	Lewna	49	18	8
	Kerr Jatta	92	35	15
	Macca Bala Manneh	69	26	11
	Samba Yassin	47	18	8
Sabach Sanjal	Bassik	41	15	6
	Kunjo	47	18	8
	Sabach Sukoto	29	11	5
	Pallen Fula	57	22	9
	Pallen Wollof	97	37	15
Total		632	239	100

Data Collection and Analysis

In collaboration with the Ministry of Agriculture of The Gambia and the Directorate of Agriculture in the North Bank Region, survey questions tailored to the local context's needs were meticulously designed. Data collection was conducted by experienced extension workers who had established strong relationships with the local farming community. The questionnaires were made accessible via mobile devices, which streamlined the data collection process. Interviews primarily took place in the evenings after household heads had completed their work on the farms. Many of these interviews were conducted directly in the farmlands, providing a richer understanding of the farmers' experiences and practices. Kobotoolbox was utilized for the initial data collection and preliminary analysis of specific indicators expressed in percentages. A more comprehensive analysis of the survey results was conducted, including the creation of diagrams and graphs to visually represent the findings, using Microsoft Excel and OriginPro.

Calculation of LVI

The LVI components were developed by examining pertinent literature related to the initial seven major components and assessing the feasibility of gathering the necessary data through household surveys. Additionally, two further major components—Knowledge and Skills, and Housing and Land Tenure—were incorporated to address two critical issues: the resilience and vulnerability of the two districts to climate change. Households with limited knowledge of climate change and a lack of diversified skills are likely to exhibit low resilience and high vulnerability to its impacts. A higher literacy rate reduces people's vulnerability to climate variability, as those who are literate have a greater variety of livelihood options. It is a well-established fact that homes located in areas susceptible to natural hazards face elevated levels of risk and reduced capacity for resilience (Kumari et al., 2023; Phuong et al., 2023).

The LVI applies a balanced weighted average approach, ensuring that each sub-component contributes equally to the overall index despite the varying number of sub-components within each major component. To guarantee equal contribution from each component, the LVI formula employs a straightforward method of applying equal weights to all major components utilizing Eq. (2) (Hahn et al., 2009).

$$\text{Index}_{sd} = \frac{Sd - Smin}{Smax - Smin} \quad (2)$$

Where sd is the original sub-component value (sometimes referred to as the raw value) for district d , $smin$ and $smax$ are the minimum and maximum values. After each is standardized, the sub-components are averaged using Eq. (3) to calculate the value of each major component. In this equation, M_d is one of the nine major components that make up the LVI, which includes Socio-Demographic Profile (SDP), Livelihood Strategies (LS), Social Networks (SN), Health (H), Food (F), Water (W), Natural Disasters and Climate Variability (NDCV), Knowledge and Skills (KS) or Housing and Land Tenure (HL).

$$M_d = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \text{index}_{sdi}}{n} \quad (3)$$

The sub-components (indicators) that comprise each major component are represented by index_{sdi} , with i indexing the sub-components and n representing the total number of sub-components in each major component. Once the values for each of the nine major components are calculated, they are averaged using Eq. (4) to obtain the district-level LVI.

$$\text{LVI}_d = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^9 wMiMdi}{\sum_{i=1}^9 wMi} \quad (4)$$

Eq. (4) can also be expressed as follows:

$$\text{LVI}_d = \frac{W_{SDP}SDP_d + W_{LS}LS_d + W_{SN}SN_d + W_H H_d + W_F F_d + W_W W_d + W_{NDC}NDCV_d}{W_{SDP} + W_{LS} + W_H + W_{SN} + W_F + W_W + W_{NDC}} + W_{NDC}HL_d + W_{NDC}KS_d \quad (5)$$

The Livelihood Vulnerability Index for district d , denoted as LVI_d , is calculated as the weighted average of the nine key components. The weights for each major component, wMi , are established based on the number of sub-components within each major component, ensuring that all sub-components have an equal impact on the overall LVI (Sullivan, 2002). In this research, the LVI ranges from 0 (least vulnerable) to 0.5 (most vulnerable) (Hahn et al., 2009).

Table 2. Indexed Sub-Components, Major Components, and Overall LVI for the Two Districts

Indicators	Lower Nuimi	Sabach Sanjal	Major component	Lower Nuimi	Sabach Sanjal
Dependency ratio	0.220	0.195	Socio-demographic Profile	0.235	0.262

Percent of female-headed households	0.073	0.010			
Percent of single-parent household heads	0.073	0.279			
Percent household heads with no formal education	0.591	0.914			
Percent of households with members needing dependent care	0.175	0.087			
Percent of households with orphans	0.277	0.087			
Percent of households with family member working in a different community	0.314	0.250	Livelihood strategies	0.494	0.473
Percent of households that depend solely on agriculture as major source of income	0.993	0.990			
Average Agricultural Livelihood Diversification Index	0.176	0.179			
Average Receive: Give ratio	0.211	0.176	Social Networks	0.488	0.623
Average Borrow: Lend Money ratio	0.400	0.740			
Percent of households that have not gone to their local government for assistance in the past 12 months	0.854	0.952			
Average time to health facility	0.142	0.400	Health	0.124	0.321
Percent of households with family member with chronic illness	0.146	0.442			
Percent of Households with Family Members miss school or work due to illness	0.058	0.317			
Average Malaria Exposure*Prevention Index	0.150	0.125			
Percent of households dependent on family farm for food	1.000	0.981	Food	0.624	0.343
Average number of months Households have challenges getting food (range: 0–12)	0.291	0.261			
Average Crop Diversification Index (range: >0–1)	0.222	0.144			
Percent of households that do not save crops	0.766	0.231			
Percent of households that do not Save Seeds	0.839	0.096			

Percent of households that have water conflicts	0.007	0.019	Water	0.210	0.060
Percent of households that utilize a natural water source	0.613	0.000			
Average Distance to Water Source	0.190	0.121			
Percent of households that do not have access to a consistent water supply	0.051	0.010			
Inverse of the average number of liters of water stored per household (range: >0-1)	0.190	0.150			
Average Number of Floods and Drought over the past 7 years.	0.162	0.315	Natural disasters and climate variability	0.374	0.289
Percent of Households that did not receive any warning about upcoming Natural Disaster	0.693	0.048			
Percent of Households with an injury or death as a result of natural disasters.	0.037	0.019			
Mean standard deviation of the daily average maximum temperature by month.	0.514	0.514			
Mean standard deviation of the daily average minimum temperature by month (from 2017- 2023).	0.500	0.500			
Mean SD of monthly average precipitation.	0.340	0.340			
Percent of Households not having TV at home.	0.737	0.856	Knowledge and Skills	0.508	0.398
Percent of Households not using smartphone.	0.204	0.471			
Percent of Households do not participate in knowledge exchange with others.	0.183	0.029			
Percent of Households that do not belong to any Fishing or Farmer-based Organization.	0.934	0.596			
Average climate change Awareness Index.	0.482	0.039			
Percent of houses with weak storm-resistant construction (wood, mud)	0.985	0.981	Housing and land tenure	0.360	0.574
Percent of households without ownership of the lands they live on.	0.015	0.019			
Percent of houses not elevated by posts/high ground to avoid floods	0.080	0.721			

Overall LVI					
Lower Nuimi: 0.372					
Sabach Sanjal: 0.340					

LVI-IPCC Contributing Factors

The IPCC-LIV Framework functions as a methodological tool for assessing and understanding livelihood vulnerability, particularly in the context of climate change. Informed by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), this framework comprises three essential components: exposure, sensitivity, and adaptive capacity, which together clarify the concept of vulnerability. The exposure of the study population is determined by the number of natural disasters recorded over seven years, as well as climate variability, which is assessed through the average standard deviation of maximum and minimum monthly temperatures and monthly precipitation data obtained from the Department of Water Resources for the same period. The adaptive capacity of the two districts encompasses their demographic profiles, the types of livelihood strategies employed, the strength of social networks, and the knowledge and skills available within the communities. Sensitivity is evaluated by examining the current conditions related to food and water security, health status, and housing and land ownership in the district, where each of the three IPCC factors is calculated using the following equation:

$$CF_d = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n wM_i M_{di}}{\sum_{i=1}^n wM_i} \quad (6)$$

where CF_d represents a contributing factor (exposure, sensitivity, or adaptive capacity) as defined by the IPCC for community d . The major components for community d are represented by M_{di} and indexed by i , while WM_i indicates the weight of each major component, with n being the total number of major components within each contributing factor. After calculating exposure, sensitivity, and adaptive capacity, the three contributing factors were combined using the following equation:

$$LVI - IPCC = (e_d - a_d) * s_d \quad (7)$$

The LVI for district d , in the above equation, represented through the IPCC vulnerability framework, is denoted as $LVI-IPCC_d$. The exposure score for community d is denoted as e , the adaptive capacity score for district d is indicated by a , and the sensitivity score for district d is signified by s .

Results

Vulnerabilities Across Major LVI Components

The analysis of LVI in Lower Nuimi compared to Sabach Sanjal reveals substantial differences in their vulnerability levels across major components and various sub-components. The vulnerability values displayed in Table 2 indicate that Lower Nuimi faces greater climate change vulnerability than Sabach Sanjal, with LVI scores of 0.372 and 0.340, respectively. The findings show that Lower Nuimi is particularly vulnerable in the dimensions of Livelihood Strategies (0.494), Food Security (0.624), Water

Access (0.210), Knowledge and Skills (0.508), and Natural Disaster and Climate Variability (0.374). While Sabach Sanjal generally performs better in these areas, it faces considerable challenges in Socio-demographics (0.262), Social Networks (0.623), Health (0.321), and Housing and Land Tenure (0.574).

Lower Nuimi records its highest levels of vulnerability in Livelihood Strategies (0.494), Knowledge and Skills (0.508), and Food Security (0.624). Food security was identified as the most critical concern for households in Lower Nuimi. Sabach Sanjal's greatest vulnerabilities lie within its values in Health (0.321), Housing and Land Tenure (0.574), and Social Networks (0.623). Both districts exhibit moderate scores in the areas of Socio-demographics and Water Access as seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Vulnerability Spider Diagram of the Major Components of LVI for the Two Districts

Vulnerability Levels in Sub-Components

In Lower Nuimi, a notable vulnerability exists among sub-components. Households in the district recorded high dependence on the family farm for their livelihood, with a dependence ratio of 100% compared to 98% in Sabach Sanjal. A significant number of households in this district do not engage in crop saving (77% vs. 23%) or seed preservation (84% vs. 10%). A larger proportion of households in Lower Nuimi rely on natural water sources (61% vs. 0%), which increases their risk from climate change impacts. Many households reported not receiving warnings for impending natural disasters (69% vs. 5%), and a considerable number do not belong to farming organizations (93% vs. 60%). On the positive side, Lower Nuimi has a lower prevalence of single-parent household heads (7% vs. 28%) and a reduced proportion of household heads without formal education.

In a similar analysis of sub-components, Sabach Sanjal reveals significant vulnerabilities, particularly among households without formal education (59%) and those not utilizing smartphones (20%). Concerns extend to the district's health services, as residents face a notably longer average time to access health facilities (19 minutes compared to 49 minutes). Sabach Sanjal also recorded a higher prevalence of chronic illnesses (44% versus 15%). Consequently, this situation leads to increased absenteeism from school or work due to illness (32% compared to 6%).

The educational backgrounds of respondents in the studied regions show a concerning gap in formal education, with 91% of participants in Sabach Sanjal and 59% in Lower Nuimi lacking any qualifications. Both districts also show a strong reliance on agriculture; however, Lower Nuimi has a slightly higher dependence on agriculture (99.3% vs. 99%) and a marginally lower Agricultural Livelihood Diversification Index (0.176 vs. 0.179). Moreover, both districts suffer from very weak storm and flood

resistance infrastructure, as the majority of households (96% and 98%) report that their homes are constructed from materials such as wood and mud.

The maximum temperatures in both districts rise in May to 39-41°C and follow a downward trend to 32-35°C throughout July and August and fall within the range of 34-37°C throughout September to December. The yearly temperature fluctuations are small but the readings showed increased values during both 2020 and 2022. The lowest temperatures occur between December and February, followed by a distinct rise in March, culminating in peaks during July and August before gradually declining until November. Rainfall is negligible from January to April, with a gradual increase beginning in May, peaking between August and September—August often records the highest totals. After September, there is a sharp decline in rainfall, resulting in little to no precipitation from October to December. Significant interannual variability is evident, as demonstrated by the notably higher rainfall during peak months in years such as 2020 and 2021, compared to other years.

Moreover, the findings illustrate that radio serves as the predominant medium for disseminating information on climate change among households in both Lower Nuimi and Sabach Sanjal, with 99% and 96% of respondents, respectively, relying on this platform. Specifically, only 37% of households in Lower Nuimi and a mere 2% in Sabach Sanjal utilize social media platforms, while television accounts for even lower engagement levels, with 21% and 4%, respectively.

LVI-IPCC for the Two Districts

In the LVI-IPCC analysis for the two districts, findings indicate that Lower Nuimi exhibits a higher exposure score (0.374) compared to Sabach Sanjal (0.289), which signifies an increased susceptibility to climate-related hazards. Both regions demonstrate comparable adaptive capacity scores (0.406 and 0.403), indicating a similar ability to respond to climate impacts. The sensitivity analysis reveals that Lower Nuimi (0.338) is more vulnerable to the adverse effects of climate change than Sabach Sanjal (0.295), as shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Values for IPCC Contributing Factors

IPCC contributing factors to vulnerability	Lower Nuimi	Sabach Sanjal
Exposure	0.374	0.289
Adaptive capacity	0.406	0.403
Sensitivity	0.338	0.295
LVI-IPCC	-0.011	-0.034

Lower Nuimi presents a higher risk profile due to its increased sensitivity and greater exposure to climate change and variability. This highlights that Lower Nuimi's increased exposure and sensitivity significantly contribute to its overall vulnerability, even though it has a slightly better adaptive capacity.

The research results suggest that stronger climate risk reduction measures and adaptive strategy improvements require immediate attention throughout Lower Nuimi. The vulnerability triangle, depicted in Figure 4, effectively visualizes the contributing factors of vulnerability for the districts of Lower Nuimi and Sabach Sanjal.

This representation elucidates the interactions among these factors, thereby enhancing the understanding of their collective impact on the livelihood vulnerabilities inherent within each district. The diagram delineates the scores for the three principal factors identified by the LVI-IPCC: Exposure, Adaptive Capacity, and Sensitivity. Exposure quantifies the extent to which these regions are susceptible to climate-related hazards. Adaptive Capacity assesses the communities' capabilities to adapt to and mitigate the effects of climate change. Sensitivity gauges the potential adverse impacts on the regions due to climate-

related changes or shocks. This diagram serves as a vital resource for policymakers and planners, providing a graphical representation of the relative vulnerabilities of each area and highlighting the need for targeted interventions to enhance resilience against climate change.

Figure 4. Vulnerability Triangle Diagram of the Contributing Factors Of LVI–IPCC For the Two Districts

Discussion

This comparative livelihood study suggests that Lower Nuimi district is more vulnerable to climate change than Sabach Sanjal. Lower Nuimi’s high vulnerability levels result from its lesser livelihood strategies, weaker food security, limited water access, and inadequate storm and flood resistance infrastructure. This has led to the district’s limited adaptive capacity while increasing its sensitivity and exposure levels to climate change. Sabach Sanjal, while somewhat less vulnerable, faces distinct challenges, including weak social networks and poor housing and land tenure, which heighten the risk of displacement during disasters. Its health vulnerabilities and fragmented community cohesion could diminish its adaptive capacity.

The high illiteracy rate (91% in Lower Nuimi and 59% in Sabach Sanjal) among farmers could hinder efforts to mechanize agriculture in The Gambia, as research has shown that educational attainment is linked to productivity levels. Education has a positive impact on the productivity of rice farming households. Educated farmers are better equipped to manage larger farms and combine inputs effectively, thereby enhancing their output (Ninh, 2021). With the advancement of agricultural technology, farmers must commit to continuous learning and skill development. Farmers today require both basic knowledge and new competencies acquired throughout their careers to navigate the evolving agricultural landscape. Ongoing professional development is vital for boosting productivity and ensuring sustainability in their practices.

The study has revealed a complete reliance on family farms in both districts for sustenance, yet, surprisingly, only 2% of farmers in Lower Nuimi and 18% in Sabach Sanjal cultivate rice, the staple food of The Gambia. In contrast, a substantial 78% in Lower Nuimi and 83% in Sabach Sanjal grow groundnuts, primarily sold to the government for export to other countries. This dependence on cash crops helps explain why a notable majority of 83% in Lower Nuimi and 98% in Sabach Sanjal report facing challenges in obtaining sufficient food for their families for an average of three months. The underlying issue is that if farmers do not grow what they consume, they must import food from other countries, leading to numerous difficulties.

The survey reveals significant differences in water and healthcare accessibility between Lower Nuimi and Sabach Sanjal. Residents of Lower Nuimi need to travel 14 minutes, whereas those in Sabach Sanjal require only 9 minutes to access their water supply, indicating that Lower Nuimi faces greater water vulnerabilities. However, individuals living in Lower Nuimi need 19 minutes to reach the nearest health center, while those from Sabach Sanjal take 49 minutes. Medical facilities, along with transport services, are lacking in Sabach Sanjal, leading to delays in medical treatment and negatively impacting health.

This significant reliance on radio underscores its critical role in delivering timely and relevant information to these communities, which may have limited access to alternative information sources. This may suggest that people consider radio an acceptable and reliable medium to understand climate-related issues, underscoring the importance of traditional media in regions where technological and infrastructural barriers may hinder the adoption of more contemporary information-sharing methods. In contrast, the survey demonstrates insufficient use of both social media and television channels to gather information about climate change. These discrepancies could indicate a digital divide in access and literacy, which limits the ability of individuals in these regions to engage in wider discussions on climate issues, often facilitated through social media and televised content. The digital gap presents an opportunity for environmental officials and policymakers to enhance the effectiveness of radio outreach by launching programs that improve digital media accessibility, thereby promoting widespread awareness of climate change among diverse groups.

Similarly, both districts exhibit comparable vulnerabilities to climate variability, particularly in terms of temperature and precipitation fluctuations. This aligns with the findings of Krubally et al. (2024), who noted that there are shared geographical and socio-economic characteristics among the regions of The Gambia, with the exception of the West Coast Region (WCR), which is closer to the Atlantic Ocean and experiences a different weather typology typical of coastal areas (Krubally et al., 2024). A significant concern revealed by the analysis is that both districts primarily cultivate groundnuts for export, which increases food security vulnerability in the areas. While rice is the staple food in The Gambia, its cultivation is not widespread among farmers. As a result, achieving self-sufficiency in food production becomes challenging without a greater focus on cultivating crops that meet the dietary needs of the majority of the population.

Conclusions

This study has explored the analytical effectiveness of the Livelihood Vulnerability Index, developed by Hahn et al. (2009), in assessing livelihood vulnerability in two districts of the North Bank Region of The Gambia: Lower Nuimi and Sabach Sanjal. Employing this framework has allowed us to compare and contrast livelihood vulnerability across various socio-economic and environmental indicators tailored to the local context. This research utilizes both primary and secondary data sources. Primary data were collected through a survey of 239 household heads, which included 9 key components and 40 sub-indicators. Two major components—Knowledge and Skills with 6 sub-components, and Housing and Land Tenure with 3 sub-components—were incorporated into the 7 major components in this study.

The comparative analysis of the LVI indicates that Lower Nuimi households are more vulnerable to climate change. The district faces challenges in its livelihood strategies and food security, underscoring its reliance on family farming for sustenance. Households in Sabach Sanjal, while less vulnerable than those in Lower Nuimi, still display vulnerabilities linked to socio-demographic factors, health, housing, and social networks. This study contributes to the existing body of research on the vulnerabilities of livelihoods to climate change in sub-Saharan Africa and comparable regions worldwide. It also provides a crucial foundation for informing policy choices and development initiatives aimed at mitigating the risks associated with climate change.

Recommendations

To effectively address these vulnerabilities, targeted policies and programs should focus on improving food security in Lower Nuimi. This can be achieved by promoting diverse agricultural practices, enhancing access to seed and crop-saving technologies, and adopting various livelihood strategies such as beekeeping, poultry rearing, basket weaving, and pottery-making. Enterprise initiatives and commercial farming aimed at both local consumption and export should be encouraged and supported by the government. Transportation networks and access to market centers are critical interventions needed to enhance the livelihood strategies of Lower Nuimi. Increasing the availability of potable water sources, such as tap pipes and boreholes, is essential to decrease the time required to obtain water and tackle water insecurity challenges in Lower Nuimi.

It is essential to enhance healthcare accessibility in Sabach Sanjal for the community. Establishing community health facilities such as clinics and Compound Health Improvement Services (CHIS) in the region will minimize the time required to obtain quality healthcare. To effectively combat chronic health problems, the government must allocate funds to local healthcare establishments and community health programs. This initiative will help mitigate the health vulnerabilities faced by smallholder farmers in the area. The central objectives of these initiatives must include two key elements: enhancing adaptive capacity and strengthening social networks, as these elements build community resilience against environmental and socio-economic challenges.

To enhance food self-sufficiency and mitigate challenges related to food accessibility for both districts, it is imperative to implement adaptation measures. These measures may include flexible labor adjustments, optimized fertilizer application, and the adoption of advanced machinery. Additionally, strategies such as crop diversification, preservation of local genetic diversity, integrated livestock farming, organic soil management, and water conservation are crucial for mitigating vulnerabilities to climate variability and addressing agricultural productivity losses resulting from climate change. Households in both districts should engage in additional income streams through non-agricultural and non-farming income-generating activities.

The study recommends that the Government and relevant stakeholders prioritize Lower Nuimi for interventions focused on improving food security and livelihood strategies. At the same time, Sabach Sanjal should be the focus for health and housing improvements. We recommend that key stakeholders enhance climate change awareness efforts by conducting outreach and workshops in both districts, using radio as the primary means of sharing climate-related information until further research indicates otherwise. The study therefore proposes establishing a more effective early-warning system to accurately predict and detect extreme climatic events and natural disasters, particularly in Lower Nuimi, but also beneficial for both districts. The successful implementation of these initiatives will require collaboration between local governments, non-governmental organizations, and community members to create a sustainable future for both communities.

The study further advocates for the implementation of a comparable vulnerability assessment in the Kuntaur, Mansakonko, and Basse local government areas. These regions are significant as they encompass a substantial population of farmers within the country. Such assessments would provide valuable insights into the specific vulnerabilities these agricultural communities face, facilitating targeted interventions and support strategies. The study thus recommends that this study be replicated in the same location over time, as this could provide valuable insights into how exposure, adaptive capacity, and sensitivity of the districts evolve as adaptation practices are implemented.

It is crucial to recognize a limitation within the methodology, specifically characterized by a degree of subjectivity, stemming from stakeholder input, involved in the selection of indicators. The employment of an equal weighting approach, whereby each component contributes uniformly to the vulnerability

scores, poses a limitation as the relative significance of each component may not consistently align across different districts. Future research endeavors should aim to refine the framework by incorporating additional secondary data on other pertinent variables, such as wind and humidity, rather than focusing exclusively on rainfall and temperature.

Data Availability

The data supporting this study's findings are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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